

WAYS TO INCREASE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SCIENCE LESSONS IN PRIMARY EDUCATION ON THE BASIS OF ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена раскрытию путей повышения эффективности уроков естествознания в начальных классах на основе передовых педагогических технологий.

Ключевые слова: Образование, воспитание, человек, личность, общество, свободная личность, педагогика, педагог, методика.

Annotation: This article is dedicated to revealing ways to increase the effectiveness of science lessons in primary education on the basis of advanced pedagogical technologies.

Keywords: Education, upbringing, person, person, society, free person, pedagogy, teacher, methodology.

Our main shortcoming was that, as the head of state said, we viewed primary education as secondary. However, the simple logic itself requires that the most mature, most experienced coaches be attached to the primary classes, where the child's worldview, language and potential are formed.

One of the factors of reforming the education system in the country is "the interests of the individual and the priority of education." As this determined the social policy of our state, a new model of education was created.

Its main initiator and leader, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev, was involved in the implementation of this model in the pedagogical process.

Based on the results of the "explosion effect" that occurs in all aspects of our lives, it is shown that:

- The process of finding one's place in life accelerates.
- leads to the formation of an independent thinker in society.
- plays an important role in realizing the potential (positive) forces of our society.
- ensures the construction of a civil, free and democratic society.

To be more precise, this model will help to take a worthy place in the world and make the Uzbek name more widely known.

It should also be noted that teachers today often confuse methodology with technology. It is therefore necessary to clarify these concepts. The methodology consists of a set of recommendations for the organization and conduct of the educational process. Pedagogical technology is the final complex of education, which renews the professional activity of the teacher.

Pedagogical technology is the process by which the teacher-educator influences the pupils (students) through the means of education and the formation of pre-defined personal qualities in them as the responsibility for this activity. It is clear from the above definition that the technological process was used as a basis in the interpretation of the concept of pedagogical technology.

In the pedagogical literature there are different forms of the term "technology". For example, "Teaching Technology", "Educational Technology", "Information Technology", "Learning Technology" and others.

While teaching technology is a concept similar to pedagogical technology, it does not mean exactly the same. Because it expresses the way of mastering specific teaching (lesson) materials within the topic and questions around a certain technology. It stands, moreover, alongside a private methodology. Pedagogical technology represents the tactics of the introduction of information technology, and the teacher - the pedagogical process, (learning (lesson) process) - the student is built on the knowledge of the laws of the functional system.

Thus, pedagogical technology differs from methodology by its flexibility, stability of results, efficiency, the need for pre-design.

It is clear from the above definitions that pedagogical technology is interpreted as the design of the learning (lesson) process on the basis of the defined primary goal and content.

In many countries, on the one hand, this technology is to some extent solved, on the other hand, it represents a certain result of attempts to introduce pedagogical technology into pedagogical practice. For many years, the theory and practice of pedagogical technology have been studied independently.

As a result, one or another methodology aimed at improving the teaching process or developing students' cognitive activity has not been able to rise to the level of technology, and has gradually lost its status and moved away from the science of pedagogy.

The combination of theory and practice allows us to determine the true nature of pedagogical technology. In our view, advanced pedagogical technologies cannot be viewed as a theory of education or as a system aimed solely at approving educational practice. Advanced pedagogical technologies mainly reflect the activities within the framework of combining theoretical and practical research in the field of education.

The use of words such as advanced, modern, and new in pedagogical technology in this article and literature has puzzled some researchers and teachers. They are now realizing that the old-fashioned approach to designing the educational process is no longer possible. So what does “advanced pedagogical technology” mean?

First, advanced pedagogical technology is designed for the educational process and is aimed at solving the set goal on the basis of the most effective methods. Consequently, each society defines a specific pedagogical system in order to shape the individual. This system is continuously influenced by social order and determines the purpose of education in general. The goal is to update the remaining elements of the pedagogical system.

At present, the National Program of Personnel Training also defines the purpose of education in a new direction, that is, to get rid of the ideological views and stereotypes of the past, to train highly qualified personnel who meet the highest moral and ethical standards in developed democracies. The purpose of education, and in accordance with it, the content has been completely renewed, so it is natural that the pedagogical process is self-renewi

Second, with the development of science and technology, the boundaries of human activity are expanding exponentially, with the introduction of advanced technologies that have a wide range of teaching opportunities in the classroom. The qualitative changes that have taken place indicate that the primary processes of “learning” are no longer in line with traditional methods and general tools, and do not correspond to the individual abilities of the teacher.

This means that there are new technical tools that require new methodologies, which are becoming an integral part of the educational process and introduce certain features into it, which are making advanced pedagogical technologies a reality.

In short, pedagogical technologies are essentially on a par with other technologies because they, like others, have their own field-specific methods and tools.

They also deal with certain “material”, but pedagogical technologies differ from production, biological, and even information technologies in that they represent a complex and incomprehensible pedagogical process as a field of knowledge related to the human mind. Its distinctive feature is that it combines the components of education with education.

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